

THE IMPACT OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT ON ACHIEVING INSTITUTIONAL EXCELLENCE: THE CASE OF GENERAL COORDINATOR OF THE GOVERNORATES IN THE KINGDOM OF BAHRAIN

AmeenaBuqais, Saeed Hameed Aldulaimi*, RadwanKharabsheh and Marwan Abdeldayem

College of Administrative Sciences, Applied Science University (ASU)
Kingdom of Bahrain, UAE

ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the impact of knowledge management on institutional excellence in the General Coordinator of the Governorates in the Kingdom of Bahrain. The researchers utilized a combined measure of the four-dimensional knowledge management standards (knowledge generation, knowledge storage, knowledge sharing, and application of knowledge) and the measurement of institutional excellence (culture of excellence, leadership excellence and human skills) to achieve the aim of the study.

The study used a questionnaire survey to collect data and distribute 162 questionnaires which were selected randomly. A regression analysis was utilized to analyze the collected data. Results reveal that the most significant dimensions of knowledge management in relation to institutional excellence were the application of knowledge (0.781), knowledge generation (0.684), while human skills is the most important element of institutional excellence in relation to knowledge management. Further, the knowledge storage was the most significant knowledge management component with an average of 3.655.

Findings reveals that Knowledge collection and storage is conducted at a very advanced level in Bahrain. Bahrain utilizes an extensive database on its population and actively collects and stores data at all levels. For instance, the ID that is carried by all residents in Bahrain (CPR) has all the relevant data on the holder and is updated regularly. Also, the use of e-banking and marketing is widely used by the government, business organizations, NGOs and the vast majority of residences in Bahrain. .

KEYWORDS

Knowledge Management, Institutional Excellence, Organizational effectiveness, Government, Kingdom of Bahrain.

1. INTRODUCTION

In a changing and increasingly globalized world, knowledge has become a source of power for both private and governmental organizations. Although knowledge is seen as the most important source of a sustainable competitive advantage in the private sector and the public sector. Public sector (service) organizations differ from their private counterparts: there is no profit-maximizing focus, there is little potential for income generation and, generally, speaking, there is no bottom line against which performance can be measured (Martinez, 2000: p. 10). Knowledge management refers to “identifying and leveraging the collective knowledge in an organization to help the organization compete” (Von Krogh, 1998). Knowledge management comprises

of practices such as creating, storing, transferring and applying knowledge (Alavi and Leidner, 2001).

Knowledge management systems have become one of the fastest growing areas in business organizations. We live in an information economy where the production and distribution of information and knowledge is the main source of wealth and prosperity (Nawab, Nazir, Zahid & Fawad, 2015). Knowledge management is one of the processes that assist organizations in generating, organizing, using, disseminating and transforming important information and expertise owned by departments that are essential for various management activities such as decision making, problem solving, learning and strategic planning (Aldulaimi, 2015).

Knowledge management aims at enhancing the performance of all organization (Kalling, 2003). The literature of management studies examines various employments of execution data (Behn, 2003; Hammerschmid et al., 2013) and presents components that influence either its training or nonpractice (Moynihan and Ingraham, 2004; Taylor, 2011). Laihonon and Mäntylä (2017) expressed that scientists have battled that open foundations utilize data generally for advancement and do not have the office to include in objective based learning. Others even contended that the instrumental utilization of execution data (i.e. an immediate connection among estimation and judgment) is uncommon (Pollitt, 2006; Van Dooren and Van de Walle, 2008). And keeping in mind that the nearness of information is a huge driver of execution (Moynihan and Pandey, 2010) administration rehearse seems to miss the practices that allow and strengthen interpretative procedures and authoritative learning in view of execution data (Moynihan, 2008). There appears to a disappointment in the general population area. The accessible reason for this disappointment of people in general area to utilize execution data is that open part establishments were made do with a positioned arrangement of order (Hartley, 2005; Osborne, 2006). Notwithstanding, data necessities are essentially associated with taken a toll control and the profundity of administration yields (i.e. units of administration utilization) (Jääskeläinen and Laihonon, 2014). The pressure, be that as it may, has moved as of late to benefit region and their long haul esteem (Hartley, 2005; Jääskeläinen and Laihonon, 2014; Pollitt et al., 2007; Sanderson, 2001). The degree of the system society and the contemplations of a more pluralist model of administration have expanded the entanglement of open administration and the decent variety of the administration data wanted (Hartley, 2005). The accentuation of management has moved from intra-institutional administration and simple information yield dialogs to between institutional administration and enthusiasm for benefit results. Laihonon and Mäntylä (2012) contended that key exercises of open knowledge management are the upgrade of between institutional information streams and agreeable procedures where targets are positive and execution data is comprehended.

Furthermore, institutional excellence has become the focus of many researchers, because the age of knowledge and information has become more sophisticated and depends on modern management methods and is no longer dependent on the human resources governed by the traditional functional specifications, but rely on human resources that are distinctive Diversity and knowledge, where transition from work, routine performance and adoption of vital systems are the effective way to achieve organizational excellence (Shelton, Darling & Walker, 2010).

The Government of the Kingdom of Bahrain has recognized the importance of improving performance at work, allowing government agencies to provide the highest level of service to citizens in terms of speed and quality. The Bahrain Center for Excellence Program aims to push institutions to reach global competitive levels of innovation, learning, transparency and knowledge, as well as a qualitative leap in the performance, services and results of the institutions

in the Kingdom of Bahrain to reach a world-class level by providing innovative scientific methodologies focusing on initiatives of improvement, empowerment, excellence and exchange. Knowledge. The center focuses on several areas, including linking performance indicators with strategic indicators to achieve the vision of 2030, instilling a culture of excellence and rooting it, investing better in the knowledge economy, leading industry and leadership teams, transforming systems into culture, and establishing monitoring and self-evaluation.

Organizations face real challenges arising from continuous external changes in information technology, new technologies and the emergence of modern management methods that directly affect the internal environment of the institutions and their performance and efficiency. As the Ministry of the Interior of the Kingdom of Bahrain seeks to implement the Government Excellence Model in pursuit of Vision 2030, these challenges need to be addressed. To meet these challenges, the Ministry has embarked on the application of knowledge management as a basic methodology. The Bahrain Center for Excellence (BCE) emphasized that knowledge management supports the institution in developing methodologies and mechanisms to support institutions through the provision of practical ways of supporting entrepreneurship and self-management knowledge and love of partnership to achieve excellence in performance and speed of response to customers and stakeholders, and reinforces the determination of the circle of creativity. Despite their application, the level of application and effectiveness of knowledge management has not been measured and whether this application has an impact on achieving the desired institutional excellence. Institutional Excellence is a state of excellence and success characterized by the institution with exceptional competitive qualities achieve its Highness and enjoy the qualities difficult to catch up, and beyond them through others (Bahrain Center for Excellence, 2009). In light of the interest of the Government of the Kingdom of Bahrain to spread the culture of excellence in government performance in order to raise efficiency and provide the best services in the public sector this study aims at examining the impact of knowledge management on institutional excellence.

2. RESEARCH MODEL

In order to cope with continuous and rapid changes, “organizations must develop improved learning methods, in particular learning from experience and knowledge applied within the organization, as well as knowledge coming from outside the boundaries of the organization” (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995). But to enable the organization to maximize the returns of knowledge requires the creation of what is known as knowledge management (Land, 2009). Knowledge management is “a systematic and integrative process of coordinating organization-wide in pursuit of major organizational goals” (Rastogi, 2000, p. 40). Knowledge management is “a discipline that stimulates an combined method to identifying, capturing, evaluating, retrieving, and sharing all of an enterprise’s information assets that include databases, documents, policies, procedures, and previously uncaptured expertise and experience of individual works” (Srikantiah, 2001, p.3). KM refers to these “tools, techniques, and strategies to retain, analyze, organize, and share business expertise” (Groff and Jones, 2003, p.11).

In reviewing the literature there are many models of knowledge management processes that have been recognized. The current study observes four variables of knowledge management that take the most consensus among scholars: knowledge generation, knowledge storage, knowledge sharing, and application of knowledge (Davenport and Prusak, 1998). Knowledge generation discusses the process in which knowledge is acquired by an institution from outside sources and those created from within (Davenport and Prusak, 1998). Knowledge sharing, also called knowledge transfer or

knowledge diffusion, refers to the process by which knowledge is transferred from one person to another, from individuals to groups, or from one group to another group (Davenport and Prusak, 1998). Knowledge utilization is the higher the effectiveness of utilizing the existing knowledge in an organization, the better the KM outcome (Ikarni and Louis, 2003).

Knowledge Management Institutional Excellence

Figure 1: model of the study.

2.1 KNOWLEDGE CREATION

Nonaka et al. (2000) defined knowledge creation as an “organizational, social and collaborative dynamic process of interactions between explicit and tacit knowledge, rather than a process of tacit or explicit knowledge alone”. Furthermore, scholars believe that knowledge creation is the action of making new understanding and concept. Researchers identified three types of knowledge-creation processes starting with encoding existing knowledge then, combining existing knowledge and use it with a historical context and, finally, production of new knowledge in order to providing information that offers new visions into the organization (Schulz, 2001).

2.2 KNOWLEDGE STORAGE

Knowledge storage is defined as the process of organizational memory formation, in which knowledge is formally stored in physical systems that are informally maintained as values, rules and beliefs associated with culture and organizational structure (Alavi&Leidner, 2001). It is known as information storage since the organization's inception, which can be used to inform decisions (Gonzalez & Martins, 2017). Knowledge storage refers to coding and indexing knowledge for subsequent reuse (Karadsheh et al., 2009). Knowledge storage is also defined as the organizational memory of an enterprise, an internal knowledge that has accumulated over time (Chang & Cho, 2008). In another definition, knowledge storage is the adoption of information programs as an aid tool that allows the use of systematic data to organize and process information and to update and modify knowledge (Alavi&Leidner, 2001).

2.3 KNOWLEDGE SHARING

Knowledge sharing alludes to "the demonstration of making information accessible to others inside the association" (Ipe, 2003, p. 341). Moreover, Davenport and Prusak (2000) propose that knowledge imparting recognizes as giving the workers to a huge information and accepting learning from others. This definition demonstrates that each knowledgesharing practices builds up both giving information and getting it. In a similar vein, knowledge sharing can likewise be characterized as a culture of interpersonal organization, implying the correspondence with individuals to trade learning, understandings and aptitudes all through a whole association. In addition, Ardichvili et al. (2003), see that knowledgesharing incorporates both the arrangement of and the demand for new learning. Further, knowledge sharing incorporates both the intentional correspondence of one's information to another, and knowledge gathering.

2.4 KNOWLEDGE APPLICATION.

Knowledge application can be characterized as "the business forms through which successful capacity and recovery components encourage a company's simple access to learning" (Lin and Lee, 2006). Knowledge portrayal and dispersion are an essential to viable utilization of information. The methodology of knowledge application incorporates recovering and utilizing information in upgrading the basic leadership process, tackling issues, expanding competency diagrams to place individuals in employments and groups to accomplish the best lift efficiency, and giving occupation aids and preparing to convey individuals up to work professionally and rapidly (Sagsan, 2006). Further, the use of knowledge gathers a scope of inclusions intended to upgrading the execution of learning to discover the strategy of treating with human issues. It is otherwise called the work process automation through knowledge connected by clients in various positions inside all divisions of the association.

The application of knowledge is also attributed to its ability to enhance the innovative activities of staff (Alavi&Tiwana, 2002). As the application of the identifier is dynamic, the application of knowledge is part of the continuous learning process, especially as the results of knowledge application enable the organization to learn and especially as it leads to changes in the attitudes and behavior of staff to support organizational learning.

3. ORGANIZATIONAL EXCELLENCE

At present, many organizations have tried to achieve excellence, but unfortunately, many have failed to achieve this goal because they do not understand the meaning of organizational excellence (Dahlggaard, 2003). Organizations working in today's global and competitive environments are constantly under pressure to improve their operations to provide high-quality outputs to stakeholders. Thus, organizations have developed strategic capabilities that combine knowledge, skills and techniques to achieve organizational excellence while maintaining competitive advantage in their markets (Islam, Ashi, Reda & Zafar, 2017). Organizational excellence during the era of globalization has become the main concern of all business organizations and has become the focus of many researchers, because the age of knowledge and information no longer recognizes the typical work governed by the functional and traditional specifications that prevailed in the old bureaucratic pyramid. Excellence and diversity of knowledge, diversity and subordinates, as the organization's achievement of outstanding performance requires its employees to move away from everything that is routine in the performance and behavior of most organizations and the adoption of vital systems and effective.

Shawqi and AL-kharsha (2008) defines Excellence as a “quality process of the practices include self-evaluation to improve the effectiveness of the organization, its competitive position, the flexibility to work in it, the participation of all the users in each organization to work together in all sections through the understanding of all activities, work to remove the error, and to improve the process towards achieving excellence”.

Bryan (2009) stated “organization that meets the conditions that set it apart from other traditional organizations in terms of: leadership, restructuring educational, and allow workers to participate, move flexibly and effectively, adopt a participation strategy, providing opportunities for the exchange of knowledge, information, strategy and culture adapted”. In Addition, organization Excellence was defined as a “crucial investment opportunities by organizations that preceded effective strategic planning and commitment to realize a common vision dominated by clarity of purpose and adequacy of resources and ensure the performance”.

It is worth mentioning that organizational excellence was one of the first developments in the knowledge revolution. It was the concept that crystallizes the basic purpose of management in contemporary organizations on the one hand, and highlights the main characteristic that is supposed to be distinguished on the other hand, and this is the clear concept of excellence. Excellence, as mentioned previously, refers to two important dimensions of modern management. The first dimension: The goal of the actual management is to try to achieve excellence and in other concept is to achieve unprecedented outputs superior to all who compete with them, and may even surpass itself from the point of learning. The second dimension: The procedures and decisions issued by the Department and its systems and activities must be characterized by excellence, absolute quality that does not give up a framework for error or corruption, and provide the real opportunities for the proper implementation of the right workers to do them correctly and completely and for the first time.

Institutional excellence requires an environment dominated by team spirit that motivates the individual to compete and cooperate with others, thus motivating the individual to continue to work in the presence of some monotony and modus operandi. Organizational excellence is therefore an important requirement for all members to improve their performance to the level which commensurate with their abilities and skills, to reach the highest level of performance (Alnaweigah, 2013). Gilgeous (1997) identified organizations excellence as the “organizations that consistently excel in the best global practices in performing their functions, which are linked to their clients in supportive and interactive relationships”. It also recognizes the capabilities of its competitors and the strengths and weaknesses of its external environment and environment.

The current study apply three measure of institutional excellence, **first** is the culture of excellence:

which refers to the integrated range of values, ethics and sustainable work practices within a given enterprise. In addition, it is a set of related values maintained by the employees of an enterprise to distinguish them from other enterprises within a single market. **Second**, leadership excellence:

The leadership has a clear impact on excellence, and this is through the growth and prosperity of individuals. It motivates them to move towards innovation and excellence through excellence in leadership abilities, active work processes and the ability to think in a modern way. Among the people to access modern ideas. The senior leadership adopts the open door strategy and supports the process of direct communication. This allows for exchanging information about the effectiveness of the organization, finding proposals and finding advanced solutions to its problems and carrying out activities that Demonstrate excellence within the organization. The

decentralized system within the institution facilitates the flow of information and innovative ideas between staff and senior leadership directly without bureaucratic impediments. Studies refer to that the creative ability of individuals is also influenced by the pattern of democratic leadership. A distinguished leader who is able to see many problems in one situation is aware of mistakes, shortcomings or deficits, and feels the problems. **Third** is the human resources which are they implement policies and strategies to adapt to challenges, to successfully implement the objectives of the enterprise, and to respond to rapid and renewed changes in the business environment. Institutional excellence involves meeting individuals' goals and organization by involving decision makers, rationally thinking and investing opportunities that need to focus on basic needs, not wasting efforts, appreciating, encouraging, developing, and training individuals, and giving them the opportunity to participate in decisions related to them. Their efforts to achieve the objectives of the establishment effectively, and the renewal of laws and regulations and directives that are being implemented to avoid the routine and centralization of dealing, and this works to achieve organizational excellence.

4. METHODOLOGY

The study population consists of all employees of the General Coordinator of the Governorates in Ministry of Interior in the Kingdom of Bahrain (Muharraq Governorate - Capital Governorate - Northern Governorate - Southern Governorate) amounting to 280 employees and employees. Random sample was utilized. Sample size was 162 as per Morgan distribution. The questionnaire received 143 and giving a response rate of 92.5%.

The questionnaire consists of (35) questions divided into two parts: 20 for the independent variable (knowledge management), 15 for the dependent variable (institutional excellence), and the first variable for the personal data of the research sample. Items measuring knowledge management were adapted from Gold et al. (2001), measuring respondents' insight of the actuality of the three knowledge management processes. As this study utilized self-reported survey to collect data to assess the variables, common method bias may be present. In order to assess the possible common method bias, Harman's one-factor test was conducted on the variables, following Konrad and Linnehan (1995). The results of the principal component factor analysis yielded 12 factors with eigenvalues greater than 1.0, which accounted for 70% of the variance. In addition, the first factor did not account for the majority of the variance (37%). It seems that common method bias is not a serious problem (Podsakoff and Organ, 1986). Table 1 shows Cronbach alpha for the study's variables which acceptable as they all exceed the recommended 0.7.

Table 1: Cronbach Alpha of the variables

Dimensions	Cronbach Alpha
Knowledge generation	0.846
Knowledge storage	0.793
Knowledge sharing	0.788
Knowledge application	0.845
Knowledge management (Total)	0.932
Culture of excellence	0.818
Leadership excellence	0.867
Human skills	0.777
Organizational excellence (Total)	0.918

5. RESULTS

The impact of knowledge management dimensions on institutional excellence results of variance analysis of multiple linear regression to test the impact of KM on institutional excellence. Table 2, reveals statistical data in the previous multiple regression table indicate that there is a statistically significant effect at the level of (0.01) for the dimensions of knowledge management on the institutional excellence (0.000), which is below the level of significance (0.05), which increases the correlation coefficient value of 0.806). It can also be said that the four dimensions of knowledge management explain 65%, depending on the value of the determination factor ($R^2 = 0.65$).

Table 2, statistical data and multiple regression analysis

Dimensions	B	β	T- value	Sig
Constant	0.892		4.589	0.001
Knowledge generation	0.222	0.274	3.455	0.001
Knowledge storage	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.998
Knowledge sharing	0.013	0.014	0.167	0.867
Knowledge application	0.499	0.581	6.878	0.001

The table above shows that the most significant dimension of knowledge management in the Ministry of Interior is the effect of applying the knowledge based on the value of (T), which reached (6.878), which is statistically significant at the level of (0.001) The value of T (3.455) was statistically significant at the level of (0.001), followed by the participation of knowledge (T) (0.167) and finally after the storage of knowledge (T) (0.002).

6. CONCLUSION

This study aimed at investigating the impact of knowledge management on organizational excellence in the general enemy of the Ministry of Interior Governorates in the Kingdom of Bahrain. The study used a questionnaire survey to collect data. A total of 162 questionnaires were distributed. Regression analysis was utilized to analyze the data. Results show that knowledge storage has a relatively weak but positive and significant impact on organizational excellence ($b=0.274$) and that knowledge application had a relatively strong but positive and significant impact on organizational excellence. No support was found that knowledge storage and knowledge sharing have an impact on organizational excellence.

The findings of the study are rather interesting and could be understood by discussing the pertaining organizational culture that exists. Knowledge collection and storage is conducted at a very advanced level in Bahrain. Bahrain utilizes an extensive database on its population and actively collects and stores data at all levels. The ID that is carried by all residents in Bahrain for example, has all the relevant data on the holder and is updated regularly, the use of E banking and marketing is widely used by Government, business, NGOs and the people. This explains why knowledge collection and storage scored high and had an impact on organizational excellence. Managers and peoples' perception of how successful and helpful the use of knowledge in this

case is important. Knowledge sharing, on the other hand is a complex issue. Bahrain has a relatively big expat community where different languages, values, norm and ways of doing business are practiced. This is both an opportunity and a challenge at the same time. Expats bring in their ways of thinking, innovation and contribute a lot to the increased innovation seen in Bahrain especially with Government Bahrain 2030 vision which aspires to transform Bahrain into a Hub in the region. The challenge is that first there may be barriers to sharing knowledge due to differing languages, values and communication styles. In addition and more importantly, there is a knowledge hoarding attitude that is widespread. People perceive knowledge as power and therefore withhold their knowledge and are less willing to share in order to increase, as they see it, their chances of acquiring more power and gain. Relevant also is the fact that business in Bahrain seems to be run by families who compete among themselves and with outsiders. This competition is healthy for the economy but comes at the cost of withholding knowledge from outsiders.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ahmed, fiaz&Shoaib, 2015. Impact of Knowledge Management Practices on Organizational Performance: an Empirical study of Banking Sector in Pakistan, FWU Journal of Social Sciences, Winter 2015, Vol.9, No.2, 147-167
- [2] Ahmed, M. (2010), "Using entrepreneurship Opportunity in optimizing Organizational Excellence : a case study", *Advances in Business Related Scientific Research Journal*, (ABSRJ), 1(1), 39-54.
- [3] Alavi, M. and Leidner, D. (2001), "Review: knowledge management and knowledge management systems: conceptual foundations and research issues", *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 25 No. 1, pp. 107-136. [Crossref], [ISI], [Google Scholar][Infotrieve]
- [4] Aldulaimi, Saeed (2015) exploring the effect of organizational culture, leadership and strategy on organizational effectiveness with mediating effect of knowledge management, *international journal of economics, commerce and management united kingdom* vol. iii, issue 4.
- [5] Alnaweigah, a. (2013). the impact of knowledge management functions on the organizational excellence from the perspective of the university of al-taif staff. *interdisciplinary journal of contemporary research in business*. 5(3).
- [6] Ardichvili A., Cardozob R., Ray S. A (2003) Theory of Entrepreneurial Opportunity Identification and Development[J]. *Journal of Business Venturing*, , 18 (1): 105-123
- [7] Armstrong, M. (2006), *Armstrong's Handbook Of Human Resource Management Practice*.
- [8] Behn, R.D. (2003), "Why measure performance? Different purposes require different measures", *Public Administration Review*, Vol. 63 No. 5, pp. 586-606, doi: 10.1111/1540-6210.00322. [Crossref], [ISI], [Google Scholar][Infotrieve]
- [9] Bryan S. (2009) the Application of Learning Organization Principles to Church Growth. Ph.D. Dissertation, Walden University.
- [10] Chang,D. R., Cho, H., (2008), Organizational memory influences new product success. *JBus Res* 2008;61:13–23.
- [11] Dahlggaard-Park, S.M., &Dahlggaard, J.J. (2003) Toward a holistic understanding of human motivation: core values – the entrance to People's Commitment? *The Int. Journal of AI & Society*, Vol. 17 (2): 150-180
- [12] Davenport TH, Prusak L. (1998), *Working knowledge: how organizations manage what they know*. Boston: Harvard Business School Press.

- [13] Davenport, T. H. and Prusak, L. (2000) *Working Knowledge: How Organisations Manage what they Know*, Harvard Business School Press, USA
- [14] Gilgeous, V. (1997). *Operations and Management Change*. London: Pitman.
- [15] Gold, A. H., Malhotra, A., & Segars, A. (2001). Knowledge Management: An Organizational Capabilities Perspective. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 18(1), 185-214.
- [16] Gonzalez, R. & Martins, M. (2017), Knowledge Management Process: a theoretical-conceptual research. *Gest. Prod.*, São Carlos, 24(2), 248-265.
- [17] Groff, T. R., & Jones, T. P. (2003). *Introduction to knowledge management: KM in business*. Burlington, MA: Butterworth Heinemann.
- [18] Groff, T. R., & Jones, T. P. (2003). *Introduction to knowledge management: KM in business*. Burlington, MA: Butterworth Heinemann.
- [19] Hammerschmid, G., Van de Walle, S. and Stimac, V. (2013), "Internal and external use of performance information in public organizations: results from an international survey", *Public Money & Management*, Vol. 33 No. 4, pp. 261-268, doi: 10.1080/09540962.2013.799803. [Crossref], [ISI], [Google Scholar][Infotrieve]
- [20] Hartley, J. (2005), "Innovation in governance and public services: past and present", *Public Money and Management*, Vol. 25 No. 1, pp. 27-34, doi: 10.1111/j.1467-9302.2005.00447.x. [Crossref], [ISI], [Google Scholar][Infotrieve]
- [21] Ipe, M. (2003) *Knowledge Sharing in Organizations: A Conceptual Framework*. *Human Resource Development Review*, 2, 337-359. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484303257985>
- [22] Islam, M. Ashi, F. M. Reda and Aasim Zafar (2017) "Strategic Knowledge Management as a Driver for Organizational Excellence: A Case Study of Saudi Airlines", *International Journal of Modern Education and Computer Science (IJMECS)*, Vol.9, No.7, pp.38-49. DOI: 10.5815/ijmeecs.2017.07.05
- [23] Kalling, T. (2003), "Organization-internal transfer of knowledge and the role of motivation: a qualitative case study", *Knowledge and Process Management*, Vol. 10 No. 2, pp. 115-126. [Crossref], [Google Scholar][Infotrieve]
- [24] Karadsheh L, Mansour E, Al-Hawari S, Azar G, El-Bathy N (2009). *A Theoretical Framework for Knowledge Management Process: Towards Improving Knowledge Performance*. *Commun. IBIMA*, 7: 67- 79.
- [25] Konrad, A.M. and Linnehan, F. (1995) 'Formalized HRM Structures: Coordinating Equal Employment Opportunity or Concealing Organisational Practices?' *Academy of Management Journal*, vol.18, no.3 pp.787-820.
- [26] Laihonen, H. and Mäntylä, S. (2017), "Principles of performance dialogue in public administration", *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, Vol. 30 No. 5, pp. 1-16. [Link], [ISI], [Google Scholar][Infotrieve]
- [27] Lee H, Choi (2003) Knowledge management enablers, process, and organizational performance: an integrative view and empirical examination. *J Manage InfSyst*; 20(1):179–228.
- [28] Lin, H.F. and Lee, G.G. (2006), "Effects of socio-technical factors on organizational intention to encourage knowledge sharing", *Management Decision*, Vol. 44 No. 1, pp. 74-88.
- [29] Ikarni, U. & St Louis. R. (2003). *Organizational Self-Assessment of Knowledge Management Maturity*. *Proceedings of the 9th Americas Conference on Information Systems* 2542-2551
- [30] Moynihan, D.P. and Ingraham, P.W. (2004), "Integrative leadership in the public sector: a model of performance-information use", *Administration & Society*, Vol. 36 No. 4, pp. 427-453, doi: 10.1177/0095399704266748. [Crossref], [ISI], [Google Scholar][Infotrieve]

- [31] Nawab, S., Nazir, T., Zahid, M. M., &Fawad, S. M. (2015). Knowledge Management, Innovation and Organizational Performance. *International Journal of Knowledge Engineering-IACSIT*, 1(1), 43–48. <https://doi.org/10>
- [32] Nonaka I (1991). The knowledge-creating company. *Harvard Bus Rev*: 96-104 (Nov-Dec).
- [33] Nonaka, I. and Takeuchi, H. (1995).*The Knowledge-Creating Company: How Japanese Companies Create the Dynamics of Innovation*, Oxford University Press, New York, NY.
- [34] Nonaka, I., Takeuchi, H. (1995) *The knowledge-creating company. How Japanese companies create the dynamics of innovation*, Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- [35] O'Reilly C. (1989). Corporations, culture, and commitment: motivation and social control in organizations. *Calif Manage Rev*; 18:9-25.
- [36] Podsakoff, P. M., & Organ, D. W. (1986). Self-reports in organizational research: Problems and prospects. *Journal of Management*, 12, 69–82
- [37] Pollitt, C., van Thiel, S. and Homburg, V. (2007), *New Public Management in Europe: Adaptation and Alternatives*, Palgrave Macmillan, Basingstoke. [Crossref], [Google Scholar]
- [38] Rastogi, P. (2000). Knowledge management and intellectual capital: The new virtuous reality of competitiveness. *Human Systems Management*, 19(1), 39-49.
- [39] Sagsan, M. (2006). “A New Life Cycle Model for Processing of Knowledge Management”, 2nd International Congress of Business, Management and Economics, 15-18th June 2006, Globalization and the Global Knowledge Economy (Edited by) Coskun Can Aktan, Selected Published Proceedings in 187-199pp., Yaşar University, İzmir. [Online access]:
- [40] Schulz, R. A. (2001). Cultural Differences in Student and Teacher Perceptions Concerning the Role of Grammar Teaching and Corrective Feedback: USA-Colombia. *The Modern Language Journal*, 85, 244-258. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/0026-7902.00107>
- [41] Shawqi, Y. AL-kharsha (2008) Leadership skills and role in the adoption of excellence strategy: analytical study in Jordanian banks. In: *Proceedings of the 1st Arab conference perpetuate excellence and competitiveness in the public and private sector institutions*, Arab Organization for Administrative Development, Amman
- [42] Shelton, C.; Darling, J & Walker, W. (2010). *Foundations of Organizational Excellence: Leadership Values, Strategies, and Skills*. LTA, (1)2, 46-63.
- [43] Shelton, C.; Darling, J & Walker, W. (2010). *Foundations of Organizational Excellence: Leadership Values, Strategies, and Skills*. LTA, (1)2, 46-63.
- [44] Srikantaih, K.; Koenig, M. (2001). “*Knowledge Management: For the Information Professional*” Medford, N.J. American Society for Information Science.
- [45] Taylor, J. (2011), “Factors influencing the use of performance information for decision-making in Australian state agencies”, *Public Administration*, Vol. 89 No. 4, pp. 1316-1334, doi: 10.1111/j.1467-9299.2011.02008.x. [Crossref], [ISI], [Google Scholar][Infotrieve]
- [46] Van Dooren, W. and Van de Walle, S. (2008), *Performance Information in the Public Sector: How It Is Used?*, Palgrave, Basingstoke. [Crossref], [Google Scholar]
- [47] Von Krogh, G. (1998), “Care in knowledge creation”, *California Management Review*, Vol. 40 No. 3, pp. 133-153. [Crossref], [ISI], [Google Scholar][Infotrieve]